

The modern conception of etiological factors, diagnosis and treatment of drug-induced hepatitis

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Received: June 01, 2023; Reviewed: June 14, 2023; Accepted: June 21, 2023

Modern medicine is supplied with a wide range of drugs. As a result of the consumption of these drugs, which are intended for the treatment of various diseases, the pathological condition that has arisen in the patient is eliminated, or its development is prevented. However, along with their effect on the assumed pathological processes, the side effects of most of these drugs were also determined. Moreover, side effects of the drugs were also detected during irregular intake of medicines without a physician's prescription. Since the main metabolic processes are carried out in the liver, this organ is most affected by the side effects of drugs. Currently, liver damage that occurs due to the drug's consumption is a confirmed pathology, and officially recognized as a disease under the name "Toxic damage of the liver" with the registered code MKB - 10 K.H. Current study provides information on the etiology, epidemiology, diagnosis, and treatment of this disease.

Keywords: Drug hepatitis, paracetamol, analgesics, statins, hormonal preparations

INTRODUCTION

The liver is a multifunctional organ that provides the exchange processes in the body and the coordinated functioning of various systems and organs. Therefore, any extreme conditions in the body may result in liver dysfunction. The last case becomes a cause for the development of the pathological process in the liver (Bueverov, 2014). Many factors affect the function of the liver and disrupt its metabolism, and one of them is drugs (Sokova et al., 2015; Zhuravleva et al., 2017). It is known that one of the most important functions of the liver is to ensure the biotransformation and elimination of drugs from the body (Pasternan et al., 2014). Thereby, the liver is exposed to the side effects of drugs, and hepatitis develops when their concentration exceeds the limit.

The increase in chronic diseases among people currently makes the use of medicinal preparations necessary. On the other hand, self-medication without physician supervision leads to an increase in the number of people suffering from drug-induced hepatitis (Eremina, 2012; Gerasimenko et al., 2013; Dvoretzki et al., 2016; Prilepskaya et al., 2016).

E.A.Ushkalova and E.A.Korovyakova showed that every year about 1 million people on Earth are exposed to the side effects of medicinal preparations. According to their information, about 180,000 people who suffer from this pathology pass

away (Ushkalova and Korovyakova, 2012). Other researchers revealed, that liver transplantation that is occurred due to abnormalities which are raised by the effect of drugs in the United States and European countries, is in a leading position (Babak and Kolesnikova, 2012; Galimova, 2011; Bjornsson et al., 2013; Chalarsani et al., 2014). The toxic damage of liver cells that occurred due to side effects of drugs can be combined into 3 groups:

1. Uncontrolled use of drugs. Indeed, today it is impossible to describe clinical medicine without analgesics and heat-reducing drugs. Although it is known that the drugs included in the mentioned group have a toxic effect, the doctor is compelling to use those drugs. However, in addition to a doctor's prescription, hundreds of people manage to improve their quality of life by using painkillers or antipyretics. This was also proved in the experiences of many clinicians (Gerasimenko et al., 2013; Eremina, 2012; Dvoretzki et al., 2016; Prilepskaya et al., 2016; Zvyachintseva et al., 2014).
2. Drug consumption for a long time due to chronic diseases. Statistics show that the number of people suffering from chronic diseases such as atherosclerosis, diabetes, and arterial hypertension has been increasing dynamically in the last decade. Certainly, to stabilize blood sugar and

atherosclerosis markers, patients are forced to use drugs until the end of their lives. It is known that the vast majority of statins and antidiabetic drugs have a negative effect on the liver. Clinical observations proved that long-term medication consumption, including statins, paracetamol, methylboron, nitrofurantoin, gilflobenakin, etc., that are used for chronic diseases, play an important role in liver damage (Dvoretzki et al., 2016; Bjornsson et al., 2013; Timasheva et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2013; Kubo et al., 2013).

3. Diet and long-term intake of herbal medicinal preparations in order to clean the body from "residual substances". E.Yu.Eremina pointed out that in recent years several drugs that are not considered medical preparation are used in a way to "clean the body from residual substances" (Eremina, 2011). The author shows that for this purpose herbal preparations, which are considered completely harmless by people, play a leading role in the toxic damage of the liver.
4. Hepatitis is caused by taking drugs. Hepatitis developed from drug addiction is considered the most severe form of drug hepatitis. It often becomes an etiological factor of liver cirrhosis or failure.

In the etiology of this disease, which is included in the literature under the name of drug hepatitis, xenobiotics along with drugs of various origins, play an important role (Gubergrits et al., 2020). Several studies revealed the toxic effect of certain drugs on the liver (Zhuravleva et al., 2017; Dvoretzki et al., 2016; Zvyachintseva et al., 2014; Butakina et al., 2016). Based on the literature data, paracetamol was predominant among drugs that cause toxic liver damage (Tantarov, 2012; Ivashkin et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2008). According to official information, obtained during the process for drug registration in Russian Federation, it was determined that 13% of the pharmacological preparations registered in 2017 contained paracetamol (<https://grls.rosminzdrav.ru/GRLS.aspx>). On the other hand, paracetamol is the most popular medicine that is used as a pain reliever and antipyretic drug in the world (Tantarov, 2012; Zvyachintseva et al., 2014). It should be noted that paracetamol and its other analogous compounds are released without a prescription, and are easy to approach for patients. In addition to paracetamol, the intake of vitamins, minerals and antiviral drugs increases the risk of toxic liver damage (Velts et al., 2017). Moreover, the negative influence of

hormonal drugs on liver function is also mentioned (Butakina et al., 2016; Ichai et al., 2006). Sufficient evidence has already been obtained about the influence of the drugs that are administered per os on the liver. It was determined that their elimination from the liver depends on several factors, including the activity of metabolites that are present in the liver blood flow, as well as the lipophilicity of the drugs. Thus, when the lipophilicity of the taken drug is weak, they are hardly absorbed and are mostly discharged from the body with the faeces. Therefore, drugs with weak lipophilicity stay longer in the body, which results in a prolonged effect on the liver. Meanwhile, when those drugs form a complex with protein, especially albumin, they easily incorporate with the enzyme in the sinusoid of the liver, pass into the endothelial reticulum, and enter the hepatocytes through the space of Disse and destroy its membrane (Gubergrits et al., 2020).

E.Yu.Eremina divides effects of the drugs based on their action on the liver into 4 main stages (Eremina, 2012).

1. Direct toxic effect of drugs on hepatocytes.
2. Toxic effect of drugs on metabolites.
3. Immune damage of the liver.
4. Idiosyncrasy.

The wide spread of drug-induced hepatitis in different populations worldwide and its fatal effect on human life have encouraged researchers to conduct scientific research on the pathogenesis of this disease. According to the research, various shreds of evidence were proposed concerning the pathogenesis of the toxic effects of drugs on the hepatocytes and based on it, two main ideas about the pathogenesis of the development of toxic hepatitis were formed. The toxic effect of drugs on hepatocytes results from the formation of reactive metabolites. Toxic hepatitis develops only after the formation of reactive metabolites. Thus, the toxic effect of drugs is achieved by producing the metabolites, which trigger immune aggression in the tissue. T.E.Polunina revealed that drugs with a toxic effect cause mild cholestasis by damaging bile duct cells and hepatocytes via blocking the transporter path of bile acids. The mixed reaction formed due to the accumulation of bile acids thus enhances the destructive effect of toxic substances on hepatocytes. This, in turn, gives a more prominent picture of the arisen cholelithiasis. The researcher calls this process microscopic cholangitis (Polunina et al., 2009).

Moroelas et al. revealed that based on USM abscess of "lost bile duct", lie the toxic effect of drugs on the liver, and the prolonged duration of this process, increase the chance of secondary biliary cirrhosis of the liver (Morales et al., 2016). The results obtained from the investigations related

to the study of the effect of the drugs on the pathogenesis of damage of the liver cells played an important role in the creation of its pathogenetic classification (Galimova, 2011; Burt et al., 2012; Lazebnik et al., 2020). In the classification proposed by L.B.Lazanbik and his colleagues, the toxic effect of drugs on the liver is presented in 2 variants.

1. The effect of drugs that directly damages the liver (type A);
2. Idiosyncrotic effects of medicinal preparations on the liver (type B).

In type A, the drug starts to damage hepatocytes at a certain dose. The latency period is short. Soon, necrosis of hepatocytes or fatty dystrophy is clearly visible on the histological picture of the liver.

In type B the toxic effect does not depend on the dose of the drug, but on the genetic characteristics of the patient. The latent period is relatively long, lasting from several days to several months.

In the classification proposed by S.F.Galimova that is based on clinical laboratory examination, the toxic effect of medicinal substances on the liver is given in 3 forms (Galimova, 2011).

1. Hepatocellular form - the concentration of ALT enzyme in the blood is increased by 2 times or more compared to the normal level.
2. Cholestatic form - the concentration of alkaline phosphatase in the blood is 2 times or higher than the upper limit of the norm.
3. Mixed form - the concentration of ALT enzyme is higher than 2 times the upper limit of the normal range, and the ALT/QF ratio is greater than 5.

This classification was supported by Ortega-Alonso et al., and slightly improved, by giving the main preference to the histological picture of the liver (Ortega-Alonso et al., 2016). The mechanism of development of cholestasis due to the medicinal preparations is given by different authors (Eremina, 2012; Gubergrits et al., 2020). E.Yu. Eremina investigated that cholestasis, which develops due to the effect of drugs, occurs according to 3 mechanisms (Eremina, 2012).

1. Obstruction of a small (cholangiolitis) or interlobular flow (cholangitis). The process occurring via this mechanism has acute progression and it is impossible to give any prognosis. In some cases, after withdrawing a medication, the process stabilizes without any additional action. Sometimes, the pathological process lasts for a long time and turns into secondary biliary cirrhosis of

the liver.

2. Failure of hepatocellular secretion of bile (cholecystic hepatitis).
3. Sclerosing cholangitis.

It was determined that the form of cholestasis depends on the nature of the drug. N.B.Gubergrits and coauthors show that inflammatory cholestasis is caused by compounds like allonurinal, azathioprine, cantopril, carbamazine, and stagnant cholesterol is caused by anabolic steroids, androgen, estrogen, and oral contraceptives (Gubergrits et al., 2020).

In some cases, the damage to the liver as a result of the effect of drugs is carried out via activation of the immune-allergic mechanism. Hepatitis that develops according to this mechanism is more acute rather than granulomatous damage.

N.B.Gubergrits et al. reported that the immune-allergic process can proceed as an autoimmune reaction (Gubergrits et al., 2020). As a result of this reaction, antinuclear and antimicrosomal antibodies are formed. However, unlike typical autoimmune hepatitis, it is possible to regulate this form of the autoimmune process by withdrawing the use of toxic drugs.

In the case of liver damage by drugs, cytolysis prevails in the form of necrotic areas, steatohepatitis, acute hepatitis, allergic reaction, and fibrosis in all 3 parts of the liver. In addition, vascular reactions that occur due to the toxic effect of drugs may appear in the form of expansion of liver sinusoids as well as occlusion of veins.

Neoplastic transformation is the most severe form of pathology that occurred in the liver due to the toxic effect of the drug. This pathology is exhibited as hepatocellular adenoma, which later can be converted to liver cirrhosis.

E.Yu.Eremina reported 5 forms of drug hepatitis (Eremina, 2012).

1. Drug hepatitis caused by an increase in the concentration of transaminase in the blood.
2. Acute hepatitis proceeding with jaundice.
3. Acute hepatitis proceeding in the pseudo-surgical form.
4. Severe acute hepatitis with liver failure.
5. Chronic drug hepatitis.

According to E.Yu.Eremina, hepatitis caused by increasing the concentration of transaminase enzyme in the blood occurs due to the prolonged intake of anti-tuberculosis drugs, methylodopa, amiodarone, statins, etc.

Cytostatics, antidepressants, and antiarrhythmic drugs play an important role in the etiology of pseudo-surgical hepatitis.

Several researchers reported that drug-induced liver damage depends on gender (Amacher 2014;

Andrade et al., 2019). Based on their research, this pathology occurs more often among women. However, other authors associate the high prevalence of drug-induced hepatitis among women with the use of oral contraceptives rather than with gender.

Moreover, due to the complications that occur during pregnancy, pregnant women are forced to take drugs and therefore may increase their chance of having drug-induced hepatitis (Sokova et al., 2015; Gerasimenko et al., 2013; Eremina, 2011; Garayeva, 2020; Shekhar and Diddi 2015; Sundaram and Bjornsson; Czeizel 2000).

Research has been carried out concerning finding the treatment of drug-induced hepatitis, and the attention of investigators is focused on the selection of pharmacological preparations that are effective for this disease. Today hepatoprotectors are the main remedy of treatment for drug hepatitis (Kucheryaviy et al., 2012; Borisova et al., 2017). There are a limited number of drugs for the treatment of drug hepatitis. Physicians mainly use Ursodeoxycholic acid, silymarin ademetonine, essential forte in the treatment of the disease.

E.Yu.Eremina revealed that ademetonine affects the main pathway of the pathogenesis of drug hepatitis, as it reduces the synthesis of glutathione in the liver and reduces its concentration. However, this statement was not admitted by other authors (Eremina, 2012).

Later N.B.Gubergrits et al., doubted the effectiveness of ademetonine since enough clinical data was not given, and thus the therapeutic effect of this drug on the treatment of the drug-hepatitis was not proven (Gubergrits et al., 2020).

Several authors reported that during the parenteral administration of ademetonine, the absorption of the drug is higher in comparison with oral administration (Eremina, 2012; Gubergrits et al., 2020). To get an effective result, N.B.Gubergrits recommended administrating ademetonine in a dose of 800 mg (during the day) into the vein and taking 1600 mg orally in the way to achieve the desired result (Gubergrits et al., 2020). Other authors prefer ursodeoxycholic acid as a universal hepatoprotector (S.G.Khomerkin and N.M.Khomerkin, 2012; Grigoryeva, 2012). I.N.Grigoryeva revealed that ursodeoxycholic acid by passing through the membrane of hepatocytes and mitochondria protects the cell from disintegration (Grigoryeva, 2012)

According to S.G.Khomerkin and N.M.Khomerkin, ursodeoxycholic acid significantly reduces the intensity of oxidative stress by halting free peroxidation of lipids and thus restores the disturbed balance of oxidants and antioxidants in hepatocytes (S.G.Khomerkin and

N.M.Khomerkin, 2012). Today, ursodeoxycholic acid is used as a liver-protective drug in the treatment of gallstone disease, cholecystitis, viral, alcoholic and medicinal hepatitis.

I.V.Borisova et al. reported that essential forte is more effective in the treatment of drug-induced hepatitis (Borisova et al., 2017). The author considers it more appropriate to first transfer 5 ml of essential H intravenously for 7-10 days, followed by 300 mg of essential forte H (2 capsules 3 times a day) for 2-3 weeks. Based on the literature review, the damage to the liver as a result of the effect of drugs is, on the one hand, the consequence of the side effects of drugs, and for another is the increase of their intake without medical supervision. Recent studies show that approximately 7% of people that take medications for a prolonged time experience adverse reactions that damage the hepatocytes and disrupt the structure as well as the function of the biliary system.

S.G.Khomerkin and N.M.Khomerkin reported that liver damage that occurs due to the effects of drugs is a process that is accompanied by structural and functional changes in the tissue (S.G.Khomerkin and N.M.Khomerkin, 2012). This idea was supported by other scientists (Ushkalova, 2012; Sychev, 2018; Ivashkin et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2008).

Thus, drugs induced liver damage is a liver pathology that is recognized under the name "Toxic damage of the liver" and registered under the code of K.71 in MKB-10. It is classified into 2 groups:

1. Idiosyncratic drug-induced liver injury (unimaginable)
2. Toxic disease of the liver (imagined).

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Dərman hepatiti, etioloji amilləri, diaqnostikası və müalicəsi haqqında müasir fikirlər

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Müasir təbabət geniş çeşidli dərman preparatları ilə təchiz olunmuşdur. Müxtəlif xəstəliklərin müalicəsi üçün nəzərdə tutulan bu preparatların tətbiqi nəticəsində xəstədə yaranmış patoloji hal aradan qaldırılır və ya inkişafının qarşısı alınır. Lakin bu preparatların əksəriyyətinin nəzərdə tutulan patoloji prosesə təsiri ilə yanaşı əlavə təsirləri də müəyyən edilmişdir. Digər tərəfdən isə həkim məsləhəti olmadan nizamsız şəkildə dərman preparatlarının qəbulunun da orqanizmə arzu olunmayan təsirləri ortaya çıxmışdır. Orqanizmdə gedən metabolizmi həyata keçirən qaraciyər olduğundan təbii olaraq dərman preparatlarının əlavə təsirinə daha çox məruz qalan orqan qaraciyərdir. Hazırda dərman preparatları vasitəsilə qaraciyərin zədələnməsi təsdiq olunmuş patologiyadır və bu səbəbdən dərman hepatiti MKB-10-da K.H. kodu ilə qeydə alınmış "Qaraciyərin toksiki zədələnməsi" adı altında rəsmi qəbul olunmuş xəstəlikdir. Məqalədə bu xəstəliyin etiologiyası, epidemiologiyası diaqnostika və müalicəsi haqqında məlumat verilmişdir.

Açar sözlər: Dərman hepatiti, parasetamol, analgetiklər, statinlər, hormonal preparatlar